

Pathogens-in-Foods Database

Final Report

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On request from the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and
Safety (ANSES) in coordination with Pauline Kooh and Anne Thebault

SUMMARY

In the twelve months of execution of Anses/IPB N° 2021-CRD-03, the Pathogens-in-Foods (PIF) database was populated with microbiological occurrence data from 212 eligible articles published from January 2020 to December 2021, selected following a SR protocol that had already been agreed upon between the parties. PIF database was also populated with data on parasites and viruses from the previous SR process. During data extraction, the system in place for step-by-step data insertion were for the first time employed and tested. Therefore, to improve the system, various changes were introduced to the food category trees, methods' trees and data sections. Furthermore, there were four main modifications implemented aiming at expediting data insertion, curation and validation: (i) the carousel data insertion system for Virus and Parasites; (ii) the capability to curate data on the Study, Bacteria, Virus and Parasite sections; (iii) the system of validation to confirm correctness of data; and (iv) the new system of users, with the added Curator type. During the one-year project, a total of 383 articles were processed for data insertion. PIF was disseminated in one e-conference. From 26 September 2022, EFSA will support further developments of PIF through the Grant Agreement GP/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01 for the next 48 months.

1. Background and Objectives of the Project

The Pathogens-in-Foods (PIF) Database and Web application (<https://fsqa.esa.ipb.pt/>) – as we know it now – was launched in November 2020, and developed with basis on microbiological occurrence data from scientific articles published between 2000 and 2017. A systematic review (SR) had been carried out following a protocol agreed upon by IPB and Anses beforehand. Literature search was completed in December 2017, and by June 2018 data had been extracted and categorised on separate spreadsheets for bacteria, parasites and viruses. Extracted data relative to bacteria were finalised and verified, whereas for parasites and viruses, the data extracted had not been verified by then.

In November 2021, PIF comprised the following functionalities: (1) a system of users: basic, advanced and administrator; (2) database architecture and food and methods categorisation trees, and relations; (3) sequence of insertion of both prevalence and enumeration data by bacteria, parasites and viruses; and (4) shiny dashboards for descriptive analysis and meta-analysis for prevalence of bacteria. It is worth mentioning that by then the only data that had been fed to the database was that of bacteria, and was entered “internally” from the spreadsheet and not manually (i.e, utilising the front-end sequence of insertion system). While sequences of insertion of data had already been developed for parasites and viruses, the data contained on spreadsheets has not been fed to PIF as yet.

In July 2021, IPB and Anses signed a Contract for Research and Development (2021-CRD-03) in order to continue the update, developments and promotion of PIF for the upcoming 12 months. Specifically, the objective of the present CRD was to complete the development of PIF with an application that allows: (1) the extraction of microbiological data according to pathogen, food category, country, type of analysis, food chain stage, with the possibility of running descriptive analysis and meta-analysis; and (2) the insertion of new contamination data by authorised users.

2. The IPB Team

Three scholarship holders were recruited for one year for the implementation of the CRD tasks: Ana Sofia Faria, Maiara Winter and Diogo Cadavez. For mini-biographies, refer to “Our Team” on <https://fsqa.esa.ipb.pt/>. Maiara Winter and Ana Sofia Faria were trained in the SR process, and rules and data insertion using PIF by Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron since 1 November 2021. Diogo Cadavez provided technical support to the database.

3. Systematic Review and Data Extraction

The SR was initiated in December 2021, with literature searches carried out for the time span of January 2020 onwards (i.e., January 2020 – December 2021); this is, PIF was to be updated with publications from the past two years. The SR protocol previously used remained the same, except for (1) the updated keywords which were enlarged in order to increase the chances of retrieving a higher number of publications; and (2) the utilisation of the free software Rayyan (<https://www.rayyan.ai/>), which allowed the experienced researcher to resolve decision conflicts of the two young researchers.

3.1 Literature search relative to food

The first literature search was carried out in December 2021 and this entailed searches to retrieve data of the 14 pathogens in foods. Table 1 presents all the terms (new and old ones) that were used in the search queries.

Table 1: Terms redefined¹ for literature search in the SR process¹ relative to food

Outcome	AND	Hazard	AND	Food	NOT	Exclude
occurrence		listeria		meat*		“challenge study”
prevalence		monocytogenes		beef		artificial
incidence		salmonella		veal		attribution
concentration		campylobacter		pork		sanitizer
contamination		bacillus cereus		"pig meat"		sanitiser
count*		clostridium		goat*		meta-analysis
		perfringens				
		cryptosporidium				

survey

sampling

“microbiological
quality”

“microbiological
safety”

“microbial quality”

“microbial safety”

detection

investigation

analysis

analyses

presence

giardia

“hepatitis A”

“hepatitis E”

HAV

HEV

norovirus

staphylococcus

aureus

yersinia

enterocolitica

toxoplasma

escherichia coli

shiga

STEC

VTEC

EHEC

O157

O157:H7

O26:H11

O145:H28

O103:H2

O111:H8

O104:H4

mutton

"sheep meat"

"lamb meat"

horse*

chicken*

poultry

broiler

fowl

turkey*

duck*

ostrich*

game

venison

rabbit*

sausage*

delicatessen

deli

“cold meats”

ham

bacon

salami

bologna

hamburger*

seafood

fish*

shellfish

crustacean*

mollusc

mollusk

clam*

oyster*

lobster*

mussel*

crab*

scallop*

egg*

dairy

milk

butter

whey

milk powder

infant powder

infant formula

baby formula

cheese*

cream

“systematic
review”

review

extract*

antimicrobial*

“essential oil*”

livestock

spiked

biofilm*

feed

supplement*

“risk assessment”

"in vitro"

"in-vitro"

yogurt
ice-cream
dessert*
pastry
cake
bread
flour
flakes
grain*
cereal*
seed*
oilseed
nut*
fruit*
produce
vegetable*
legume*
salad*
sprout*
spice*
"vegan food*"
veggie
drink*
juice*
beverage*
"bottled water"
composite
multi-
ingredient
"complex
food"
ready-to-eat
RTE

¹Highlighted in yellow are those terms newly introduced in the search

The terms were then accommodated in formulas according to the literature search engine's syntax. Searches were done on the 5 December 2021 using the following formula:

Web of Science:

TS=(occurrence OR prevalence OR incidence OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR survey OR sampling OR "microbiological quality" OR "microbiological safety" OR "microbial quality" OR "microbial safety" OR detection OR investigation OR analysis OR analyses OR presence) AND TS=(listeria monocytogenes OR salmonella OR campylobacter OR bacillus cereus OR clostridium perfringens OR cryptosporidium OR giardia OR "hepatitis A" OR "hepatitis E" OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR staphylococcus aureus OR yersinia enterocolitica OR toxoplasma OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4))) AND TS=(meat* OR beef OR veal OR pork OR "pig meat" OR goat* OR mutton

OR "sheep meat" OR "lamb meat" OR horse* OR chicken* OR poultry OR broiler OR fowl OR turkey* OR duck* OR ostrich* OR game OR venison OR rabbit* OR sausage* OR delicatessen OR deli OR "cold meats" OR ham OR bacon OR salami OR bologna OR hamburger* OR seafood OR fish* OR shellfish OR crustacean* OR mollusc OR mollusk OR clam* OR oyster* OR lobster* OR mussel* OR crab* OR scallop* OR egg* OR dairy OR milk OR butter OR whey OR milk powder OR infant powder OR infant formula OR baby formula OR cheese* OR cream OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR dessert* OR pastry OR cake OR bread OR flour OR flakes OR grain* OR cereal* OR seed* OR oilseed OR nut* OR fruit* OR produce OR vegetable* OR legume* OR salad* OR sprout* OR spice* OR "vegan food*" OR veggie OR drink* OR juice* OR beverage* OR "bottled water" OR composite OR multi-ingredient OR "complex food" OR ready-to-eat OR RTE) NOT TS=("challenge study" OR artificial OR attribution OR sanitizer OR sanitiser OR meta-analysis OR "systematic review" OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR "essential oil*" OR livestock OR spiked OR biofilm* OR feed OR supplement* OR "risk assessment" OR "in vitro" OR "in-vitro")

SciELO:

(subject:(occurrence OR prevalence OR incidence OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR survey OR sampling OR "microbiological quality" OR "microbiological safety" OR "microbial quality" OR "microbial safety" OR detection OR investigation OR analysis OR analyses OR presence)) AND (subject:(listeria monocytogenes OR salmonella OR campylobacter OR bacillus cereus OR clostridium perfringens OR cryptosporidium OR giardia OR "hepatitis A" OR "hepatitis E" OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR staphylococcus aureus OR yersinia enterocolitica OR toxoplasma OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)))) AND (subject:(meat* OR beef OR veal OR pork OR "pig meat" OR goat* OR mutton OR "sheep meat" OR "lamb meat" OR horse* OR chicken* OR poultry OR broiler OR fowl OR turkey* OR duck* OR ostrich* OR game OR venison OR rabbit* OR sausage* OR delicatessen OR deli OR "cold meats" OR ham OR bacon OR salami OR bologna OR hamburger* OR seafood OR fish* OR shellfish OR crustacean* OR mollusc OR mollusk OR clam* OR oyster* OR lobster* OR mussel* OR crab* OR scallop* OR egg* OR dairy OR milk OR butter OR whey OR milk powder OR infant powder OR infant formula OR baby formula OR cheese* OR cream OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR dessert* OR pastry OR cake OR bread OR flour OR flakes OR grain* OR cereal* OR seed* OR oilseed OR nut* OR fruit* OR produce OR vegetable* OR legume* OR salad* OR sprout* OR spice* OR "vegan food*" OR veggie OR drink* OR juice* OR beverage* OR "bottled water" OR composite OR multi-ingredient OR "complex food" OR ready-to-eat OR RTE)) AND NOT (subject:(("challenge study" OR artificial OR attribution OR sanitizer OR sanitiser OR meta-analysis OR "systematic review" OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR "essential oil*" OR livestock OR spiked OR biofilm* OR feed OR supplement* OR "risk assessment" OR "in vitro" OR "in-vitro"))

SCOPUS:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (occurrence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (prevalence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (incidence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (concentration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (contamination) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (count*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (survey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sampling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbiological quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbiological safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbial quality") OR TITLE-ABS-

KEY ("microbial safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (detection) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (investigation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (analyses) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (presence)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (listeria monocytogenes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salmonella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (campylobacter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bacillus cereus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (clostridium perfringens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cryptosporidium) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (giardia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("hepatitis A") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("hepatitis E") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (HAV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (HEV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (norovirus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (staphylococcus aureus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (yersinia enterocolitica) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (toxoplasma) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY (escherichia coli) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (shiga) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (STEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (VTEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (EHEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157:H7) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O26:H11) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O145:H28) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O103:H2) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O111:H8) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O104:H4))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (meat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (beef) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (veal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (pork) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("pig meat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (goat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mutton) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("sheep meat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("lamb meat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (horse*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (chicken*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (poultry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (broiler) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fowl) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (turkey*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (duck*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ostrich*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (game) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (venison) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (rabbit*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sausage*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (delicatessen) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (deli) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("cold meats") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ham) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bacon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salami) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bologna) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (hamburger*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (seafood) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fish*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (shellfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (crustacean*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mollusc) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mollusk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (clam*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (oyster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (lobster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mussel*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (crab*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (scallop*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (egg*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dairy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (butter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (whey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk powder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (infant powder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (infant formula) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (baby formula) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cheese*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (yogurt) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ice-cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dessert*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (pastry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cake) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bread) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (flour) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (flakes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (grain*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cereal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (seed*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (oilseed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (nut*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fruit*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (produce) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (vegetable*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (legume*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salad*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sprout*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("vegan food*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (veggie) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (drink*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (juice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (beverage*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("bottled water") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (composite) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (multi-ingredient) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("complex food") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ready-to-eat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (RTE)) AND NOT (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("challenge study") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (artificial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (attribution) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitizer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitiser) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (meta-analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("systematic review") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (review) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (extract*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (antimicrobial*) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("essential oil*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (livestock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spiked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (biofilm*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (feed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (supplement*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("risk assessment") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in-vitro")

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((occurrence[Title/Abstract]) OR (prevalence[Title/Abstract]) OR (incidence[Title/Abstract]) OR (concentration[Title/Abstract]) OR (contamination[Title/Abstract]) OR (count*[Title/Abstract]) OR (survey[Title/Abstract]) OR (sampling[Title/Abstract]) OR ("microbiological quality"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("microbiological safety"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("microbial quality"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("microbial safety"[Title/Abstract]) OR (detection[Title/Abstract]) OR (investigation[Title/Abstract]) OR (analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR (analyses[Title/Abstract]) OR (presence[Title/Abstract])) AND ((listeria monocytogenes[Title/Abstract]) OR (salmonella[Title/Abstract]) OR (campylobacter[Title/Abstract]) OR (bacillus cereus[Title/Abstract]) OR (clostridium perfringens[Title/Abstract]) OR (cryptosporidium[Title/Abstract]) OR (giardia[Title/Abstract]) OR ("hepatitis A"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("hepatitis E"[Title/Abstract]) OR (HAV[Title/Abstract]) OR (HEV[Title/Abstract]) OR (norovirus[Title/Abstract]) OR (staphylococcus aureus[Title/Abstract]) OR (yersinia enterocolitica[Title/Abstract]) OR (toxoplasma[Title/Abstract]) OR ((escherichia coli[Title/Abstract]) AND ((shiga[Title/Abstract]) OR (STEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (VTEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (EHEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157:H7[Title/Abstract]) OR (O26:H11[Title/Abstract]) OR (O145:H28[Title/Abstract]) OR (O103:H2[Title/Abstract]) OR (O111:H8[Title/Abstract]) OR (O104:H4[Title/Abstract]))) AND ((meat*[Title/Abstract]) OR (beef[Title/Abstract]) OR (veal[Title/Abstract]) OR (pork[Title/Abstract]) OR ("pig meat"[Title/Abstract]) OR (goat*[Title/Abstract]) OR (mutton[Title/Abstract]) OR ("sheep meat"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("lamb meat"[Title/Abstract]) OR (horse*[Title/Abstract]) OR (chicken*[Title/Abstract]) OR (poultry[Title/Abstract]) OR (broiler[Title/Abstract]) OR (fowl[Title/Abstract]) OR (turkey*[Title/Abstract]) OR (duck*[Title/Abstract]) OR (ostrich*[Title/Abstract]) OR (game[Title/Abstract]) OR (venison[Title/Abstract]) OR (rabbit*[Title/Abstract]) OR (sausage*[Title/Abstract]) OR (delicatessen[Title/Abstract]) OR (deli[Title/Abstract]) OR ("cold meats"[Title/Abstract]) OR (ham[Title/Abstract]) OR (bacon[Title/Abstract]) OR (salami[Title/Abstract]) OR (bologna[Title/Abstract]) OR (hamburger*[Title/Abstract]) OR (seafood[Title/Abstract]) OR (fish*[Title/Abstract]) OR (shellfish[Title/Abstract]) OR (crustacean*[Title/Abstract]) OR (mollusc[Title/Abstract]) OR (mollusk[Title/Abstract]) OR (clam*[Title/Abstract]) OR (oyster*[Title/Abstract]) OR (lobster*[Title/Abstract]) OR (mussel*[Title/Abstract]) OR (crab*[Title/Abstract]) OR (scallop*[Title/Abstract]) OR (egg*[Title/Abstract]) OR (dairy[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk[Title/Abstract]) OR (butter[Title/Abstract]) OR (whey[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk powder[Title/Abstract]) OR (infant powder[Title/Abstract]) OR (infant formula[Title/Abstract]) OR (baby formula[Title/Abstract]) OR (cheese*[Title/Abstract]) OR (cream[Title/Abstract]) OR (yogurt[Title/Abstract]) OR (ice-cream[Title/Abstract]) OR (dessert*[Title/Abstract]) OR (pastry[Title/Abstract]) OR (cake[Title/Abstract]) OR (bread[Title/Abstract]) OR (flour[Title/Abstract]) OR (flakes[Title/Abstract]) OR (grain*[Title/Abstract]) OR (cereal*[Title/Abstract]) OR (seed*[Title/Abstract]) OR (oilseed[Title/Abstract]) OR (nut*[Title/Abstract]) OR (fruit*[Title/Abstract]) OR (produce[Title/Abstract]) OR (vegetable*[Title/Abstract]) OR (legume*[Title/Abstract]) OR (salad*[Title/Abstract]) OR (sprout*[Title/Abstract]) OR (spice*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("vegan

food*[Title/Abstract]) OR (veggie[Title/Abstract]) OR (drink*[Title/Abstract]) OR (juice*[Title/Abstract]) OR (beverage*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("bottled water"[Title/Abstract]) OR (composite[Title/Abstract]) OR (multi-ingredient[Title/Abstract]) OR ("complex food"[Title/Abstract]) OR (ready-to-eat[Title/Abstract]) OR (RTE[Title/Abstract])) NOT (("challenge study"[Title/Abstract]) OR (artificial[Title/Abstract]) OR (attribution[Title/Abstract]) OR (sanitizer[Title/Abstract]) OR (sanitiser[Title/Abstract]) OR (meta-analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR ("systematic review"[Title/Abstract]) OR (review[Title/Abstract]) OR (extract*[Title/Abstract]) OR (antimicrobial*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("essential oil*[Title/Abstract]) OR (livestock[Title/Abstract]) OR (spiked[Title/Abstract]) OR (biofilm*[Title/Abstract]) OR (feed[Title/Abstract]) OR (supplement*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("risk assessment"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("in vitro"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("in-vitro"[Title/Abstract]))

Results were further filtered for type of paper (retaining articles and early access), countries (retaining all European) and languages (retaining English, French, Spanish and Portuguese).

3.2 Literature search relative to water

The second literature search was carried out in February 2022 and this entailed searches to retrieve data of the 14 pathogens in water other than bottled water. The terms used for literature search were the same as in Table 1, except for the keywords linked to Food, which were replaced by keywords linked to water; namely: "water treatment*", "water reservoir*", "water tank*", "water tower*", "tap water" and "drinking water". Such terms were concatenated in the following formula:

Web of Science:

TS=(occurrence OR prevalence OR incidence OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR survey OR sampling OR "microbiological quality" OR "microbiological safety" OR "microbial quality" OR "microbial safety" OR detection OR investigation OR analysis OR analyses OR presence) AND TS=(listeria monocytogenes OR salmonella OR campylobacter OR bacillus cereus OR clostridium perfringens OR cryptosporidium OR giardia OR "hepatitis A" OR "hepatitis E" OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR staphylococcus aureus OR yersinia enterocolitica OR toxoplasma OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4))) AND TS=("water treatment*" OR "water reservoir*" OR "water tank*" OR "water tower*" OR "tap water" OR "drinking water") NOT TS=("challenge study" OR artificial OR attribution OR sanitizer OR sanitiser OR meta-analysis OR "systematic review" OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR "essential oil*" OR livestock OR spiked OR biofilm* OR feed OR supplement* OR "risk assessment" OR "in vitro" OR "in-vitro")

SCIELO:

(subject:(occurrence OR prevalence OR incidence OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR survey OR sampling OR “microbiological quality” OR “microbiological safety” OR “microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR detection OR investigation OR analysis OR analyses OR presence)) AND (subject:(listeria monocytogenes OR salmonella OR campylobacter OR bacillus cereus OR clostridium perfringens OR cryptosporidium OR giardia OR “hepatitis A” OR “hepatitis E” OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR staphylococcus aureus OR yersinia enterocolitica OR toxoplasma OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)))) AND (subject:("water treatment*" OR "water reservoir*" OR "water tank*" OR "water tower*" OR "tap water" OR "drinking water")) AND NOT (subject:(“challenge study” OR artificial OR attribution OR sanitizer OR sanitiser OR meta-analysis OR “systematic review” OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR “essential oil*” OR livestock OR spiked OR biofilm* OR feed OR supplement* OR “risk assessment” OR "in vitro" OR "in-vitro"))

SCOPUS:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (occurrence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (prevalence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (incidence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (concentration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (contamination) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (count*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (survey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sampling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“microbiological quality”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“microbiological safety”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“microbial quality”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“microbial safety”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (detection) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (investigation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (analyses) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (presence)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (listeria monocytogenes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salmonella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (campylobacter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bacillus cereus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (clostridium perfringens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cryptosporidium) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (giardia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“hepatitis A”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“hepatitis E”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (HAV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (HEV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (norovirus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (staphylococcus aureus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (yersinia enterocolitica) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (toxoplasma) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY (escherichia coli) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (shiga) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (STEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (VTEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (EHEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157:H7) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O26:H11) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O145:H28) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O103:H2) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O111:H8) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O104:H4))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("water treatment*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("water reservoir*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("water tank*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("water tower*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("tap water") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("drinking water")) AND NOT (TITLE-ABS-KEY (“challenge study”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (artificial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (attribution) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitizer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitiser) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (meta-analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“systematic review”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (review) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (extract*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (antimicrobial*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“essential oil*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (livestock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spiked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (biofilm*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (feed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (supplement*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“risk assessment”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in-vitro"))

PubMed:

((occurrence[Title/Abstract]) OR (prevalence[Title/Abstract]) OR (incidence[Title/Abstract]) OR (concentration[Title/Abstract]) OR (contamination[Title/Abstract]) OR (count*[Title/Abstract]) OR (survey[Title/Abstract]) OR (sampling[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbiological quality”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbiological safety”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbial quality”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbial safety”[Title/Abstract]) OR (detection[Title/Abstract]) OR (investigation[Title/Abstract]) OR (analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR (analyses[Title/Abstract]) OR (presence[Title/Abstract])) AND ((listeria monocytogenes[Title/Abstract]) OR (salmonella[Title/Abstract]) OR (campylobacter[Title/Abstract]) OR (bacillus cereus[Title/Abstract]) OR (clostridium perfringens[Title/Abstract]) OR (giardia[Title/Abstract]) OR (“hepatitis A”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“hepatitis E”[Title/Abstract]) OR (HAV[Title/Abstract]) OR (HEV[Title/Abstract]) OR (norovirus[Title/Abstract]) OR (staphylococcus aureus[Title/Abstract]) OR (yersinia enterocolitica[Title/Abstract]) OR (toxoplasma[Title/Abstract]) OR ((escherichia coli[Title/Abstract]) AND ((shiga[Title/Abstract]) OR (STEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (VTEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (EHEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157:H7[Title/Abstract]) OR (O26:H11[Title/Abstract]) OR (O145:H28[Title/Abstract]) OR (O103:H2[Title/Abstract]) OR (O111:H8[Title/Abstract]) OR (O104:H4[Title/Abstract]))) AND (“water treatment”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“water reservoir”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“water tank”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“water tower”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“tap water”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“drinking water”[Title/Abstract])) NOT (“challenge study”[Title/Abstract]) OR (artificial[Title/Abstract]) OR (attribution[Title/Abstract]) OR (sanitizer[Title/Abstract]) OR (sanitiser[Title/Abstract]) OR (meta-analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR (“systematic review”[Title/Abstract]) OR (review[Title/Abstract]) OR (extract*[Title/Abstract]) OR (antimicrobial*[Title/Abstract]) OR (“essential oil”[Title/Abstract]) OR (livestock[Title/Abstract]) OR (spiked[Title/Abstract]) OR (biofilm*[Title/Abstract]) OR (feed[Title/Abstract]) OR (supplement*[Title/Abstract]) OR (“risk assessment”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“in vitro”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“in-vitro”[Title/Abstract]))

3.3 De-duplicate, screening and eligibility assessment

BibTeX files from the searches on WoS, SciELO, PubMed and Scopus were combined in a single file using the software Zotero for the food and the water searches, respectively. Removal of duplicates was carried out by the two young researchers using Zotero; and in the end, deduplicated entries amounted to 2587 references (Figure 1). BibTeX files containing deduplicated records are called 2020_2021Dec_WithoutDups_Food.BibTeX and 2020_2021Dec_WithoutDups_Water.BibTeX and are in the annex. The following steps of abstract screening and eligibility assessment were undertaken as per the SR protocol, following the same pre-established rules, yet, utilising the Rayyan software. This software allowed the remote resolution of conflicts in the accept/reject decisions between the two reviewers by the

experienced reviewer. Eligibility assessment was finalised by the end of March 2021. Before the stage of data extraction, a total of 205 publications was considered as eligible for inclusion in PIF. The file **2020_2021Dec_Clean.BibTeX** contains these records. Bear in mind that these are the records before data extraction/insertion.

Figure 1: PRISMA chart of the stages of the systematic review of microbiological occurrence data published between Jan 2020 and Dec 2021

*Records kept in BibTeX files annexed

3.4 Insertion of data on PIF

During data extraction, it was realised that some articles (n=44) could not be processed because important information (such as sample size or sample weight for analysis) was missing. Therefore, data from those initially-selected articles could not be extracted in the end. In the same way, during data extraction, it was also possible to add publication records. For instance, one entry was a report that compiled microbiological results from other sources, therefore forwarding the reviewers to search the original papers. The same occurred in a few articles focusing on the molecular identification of foodborne pathogens, from a pool of strains that had been isolated from microbiological surveys published elsewhere. For such reasons, during the phase of data insertion, still other articles (n=7 records) were added to the BibTeX file. Furthermore, there were records (n=3) whose full-length papers were not readily available, and, hence, data could not be extracted from those sources (Figure 1). The final publication records after data insertion are contained on the file **2020_2021Dec_Clean_Final.BibTeX**. In this file, the entries added at a later stage are marked by a green flag, the removed entries (not inserted) marked with the yellow eye, and the missing full-length papers marked with a red flag. The 165 records whose data were extracted and inserted on PIF were not assigned any kind of mark on the BibTeX file.

Although the step-by-step data insertion system had been implemented in November 2020, insertion of data using this means had not been tried before. It was during the execution of this project that the systems of data insertion for bacteria, parasites and viruses were for the first time tested. Therefore, insertion of data through the platform put in evidence that some corrections and improvements to the system needed to be carried out; and these were introduced. Table 2 lists the changes done on the PIF exclusively related to the data insertion system.

Table 2: Alterations performed on the PIF data insertion system pertaining food category trees, methods' trees and data sections

Type	Level	Before	After
Tree of food categories and related variables	New Subcategories within the Category "Beverage"	Beverages ... Water	Beverages ... Water TapWater OtherWater

			Specify:_____
	New ClassSpecie within the Subcategory "Milk"	Milk ... Ovine	Milk ... Ovine Human
	New FoodClass within the Category "Dairy"	Dairy Raw Pasteurised	Dairy Raw Pasteurised NA
	New OrganSampled levels when "Stage" is MidProcessing and "Category" is Meat	OrganSampled Diaphragm MeatJuice Liver Heart	OrganSampled Diaphragm MeatJuice Liver Heart Brain Blood
	New PackStatus levels	PackStatus Packed Unpacked	PackStatus Packed Unpacked Various NA
	New TempRetail levels	TempRetail Ambient Chill Frozen Various	TempRetail Ambient Chill Frozen Various NA
	New FoodOrigin levels	FoodOrigin ...	FoodOrigin ... Multiple CentralEurope EastEurope NorthEurope SouthEurope WestEurope
Tree of methods for Parasites	A free-text field added when Other is selected within Sample Preparation	EssaySamplePrep ... Other	Beverages ... Other Specify:_____
	New ParasiteUnit levels	ParasiteUnit Oocysts Tachyzoites Cysts Other	ParasiteUnit Oocysts Tachyzoites Cysts Other NA
Section STUDY	-	CountryPublication was field forgotten in the data insertion system	CountryPublication added as a field with drop-down options when registering a study
Section BACTERIA	Box of Results for the Enumeration section	The fields CountsModel and MeanConcentration were independent	The field CountsModel is mandatory only when the MeanConcentration is filled
Section PARASITES	Box of General Results		The fields BiasPotential, Reason and Comments were added

4. Main Modifications Introduced to the PIF system

Four important modifications were introduced to the PIF system in order to expedite data insertion, curation and validation.

- a) Sections VIRUS and PARASITE: A carousel system of data insertion was introduced to feed data of different foods or different agents from the same study. This was implemented in the same manner as that of BACTERIA.
- b) Data curation: The option CURATE was introduced in the four sections – STUDY, BACTERIA, VIRUS and PARASITE. “Curate Data” will retrieve the data and present it to the curator on the same carousel system used for insertion.
- c) System of validation: The fields “User”, “Validated” (yes/no) and “ValidatedBy” were created in order to verify the correctness of the data inserted. “User” automatically stores the ID of the person that created the sample entry. After checking the correctness of the data inserted in the sample entry, the administrator is presented with the option “Validated” (yes/no) at the end of the carousel. After validation, the sample entry will also have the “ValidatedBy” field filled with the administrator ID. The system of validation proved to be useful during training of the young researchers.
- d) System of users: Before the project, PIF could be accessed by three types of users: Basic user, who could access to descriptive stats, meta-analysis and data, yet without having access to the sources (BibTeX files), the Advanced user, who in addition could download the sources (BibTeX files) of their data selections, and the Admin user, who can insert and delete sample entries. In addition to those users, the Curator user was created to be able to insert and curate sample entries. Now, the Admin user has also the faculty to realise the final validation of data.

5. Insertion of Data from Previous SR

As pointed out in Section 1, the occurrence data of parasites and viruses from the previous SR had been extracted on a spreadsheet, and had not been verified for quality nor for completeness. Therefore, during the implementation of the current CRD, it was decided that the data from these eligible records would be extracted again, but using the insertion system of the platform. The number of eligible records amounted to 80 for parasites and 104 for viruses. Data from

those articles started to be inserted on PIF since July 2022. Figure 2 schematises the number of virus-related entries whose data were inserted on PIF, as well as the number of references that did not meet the requirements for data insertion. Extraction of data pertaining to viruses was finalised in September 2022.

Figure 2: Summary of entries inserted on PIF for viruses from previous systematic review

Figure 3 schematises the number of parasite-related entries whose data were inserted on PIF, as well as the number of references that did not meet the requirements for data insertion. Extraction of data pertaining to parasites is ongoing (59 papers still to insert) and will be finalised in October 2022.

Figure 3: Summary of entries inserted on PIF for parasites from previous systematic review (at the time of writing the current report)

6. Dissemination of PIF Database

PIF database has been disseminated at the 3rd International Electronic Conference on Foods: Food, Microbiome, and Health - A Celebration of the 10th Anniversary of Foods' Impact on Our Wellbeing session Foods Quality and Safety, through the abstract and proceedings paper entitled “Pathogens-in-Foods database: a web application for assessing the occurrence data of microbiological hazards in foods marketed in Europe”, authored by A. S. Faria, M. Winter, A. Thebault, L. Guillier, M. Sanaa, P. Kooh, V. Cadavez and U. Gonzales-Barron. This paper introduces the advantages of the PIF database, details the process for data selection and inclusion, and summarises the extraction of data from the web application by the user. Abstract and papers links follow:

<https://sciforum.net/paper/view/13014>

<https://sciforum.net/manuscripts/13014/manuscript.pdf>

On the 23rd June 2022, IPB and Anses signed the Grant Agreement GP/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01 with EFSA with the objective of maintaining the PIF database while making the SR protocol transparent and in line with EFSA guidelines and terminology. The project started on 26 September 2022 and has a duration of 48 months.

7. Appendices

Resources of PIF can be downloaded from the Zenodo Community PIF at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/pif/>.

- 1) Conference paper “Pathogens-in-Foods database: a web application for assessing the occurrence data of microbiological hazards in foods marketed in Europe”, Faria, Ana Sofia; Winter, Maiara; Thebault, Anne; Guillier, Laurent; Sanaa, Moez; Kooh, Pauline; Cadavez, Vasco; Gonzales-Barron, Ursula.
- 2) Zip file “BibTeX files comprising records Jan 2020-Dec202”, which contains:
2020-2021Dec_WithoutDups_Food.BibTeX: de-duplicated records of literature search pertaining food terms, carried out in December 2021

2020-2021Dec_WithoutDups_Water.BibTeX: de-duplicated records of literature search pertaining only water terms, carried out in February 2022

2020-2021Dec_Clean.BibTeX: eligible records ready for insertion on PIF database

2020-2021Dec_Clean_Final.BibTeX: final records whose data were inserted on PIF database, covering publications between Jan 2020 and Dec 2021